

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder

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Abstract

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in recent years is one of the most frequently described and diagnosed disorders in school-age children. Among children who cause educational problems, and from early childhood, there is a group of restless, overly mobile and active children, with a changing and impulsive mood. The reasons for the development of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder are not fully known. These are very complex mechanisms and require knowledge in various fields of medicine. The functioning of a child with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is determined on the one hand by his or her own abilities and on the other hand constantly shaped by experience gained as a result of interaction with the environment. Choosing the right therapeutic method for a hyperactive psychomotor child is not easy, because it is necessary to take into account the sphere in which hyperactivity occurs and the depth of its severity. Therapy is selected to the specific needs of the child, his personality, individual situation. The aim of the article is to characterize the notion of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and to approximate the methods that are used for therapy.

Keywords: : Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, ADHD, types of ADHD

Introduction

At a time when society is living faster and faster in the pursuit of widely understood success, the lifestyle of people has changed significantly, and thus the model of education has changed. Among children, more and more often we meet children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, usually referred to as a children with ADHD, and this is one of the most common developmental disorders. This growing group of children is very difficult to function at home as well as in kindergarten or school. They are often treated as very difficult children. They require, above all, acceptance but also special methods of work and upbringing. Increasingly, these children must be treated and they should have therapy. So far, however, no treatment methods have been developed that would be effective against the whole group of children affected by this disorder. The aim of the article is to characterize the notion of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and to present methods that are used for therapy.

1. The notion of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, referred to in the literature as "attention deficit hyperactivity disorder" or "hyperkinetic disorder" is a group of disorders characterized by „ early onset (usually in the first five years of life), lack of perseverance in

tasks requiring cognitive involvement, a tendency to move from one activity to another without completing any of them and a disorganized, poorly controlled excessive activity "[1]. Thus, ADHD, or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, is a disease state characterized by brain disorder (a significant predominance of stimulation over inhibition) that makes a person have difficulty controlling behavior and maintaining concentration.

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a "medical diagnosis, applied to children and adults who have severe cognitive difficulties and behavioral disorders in important aspects of their lives (eg in family and personal relationships, personal school or at work)"[2]. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in recent years is one of the most frequently described and diagnosed disorders in school-age children. Among children who cause educational problems, and from early childhood is a group of restless, overly mobile and active children, with a changing and impulsive mood. Due to the presented behaviors, they are called hyperactive psychomotor children[3].

Depending on the diagnostic criteria used, it is considered that the incidence of ADHD varies between 3 - 8% of the population of children at a younger school age. But according to the aforementioned definition, ADHD also applies to children in old school age[4]. The symptoms look a bit

different. In place of increased physical activity (characteristic for pre-school and younger school age) emotional hyper-reactivity associated with growing up and puberty appears.

Currently, depending on the type of classification, two basic names are used to define attention deficit hyperactivity disorder:

1. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder with concentration disorders - ADHD according to DSM - IV (classification of the American Psychiatric Association)

2. Hyperkinetic syndrome - according to ICD-10 (World Health Organization classification).

Diagnosis of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is made on the basis of criteria accepted and recognized by the above classifications[4].

The basis for the diagnosis of ADHD is therefore the triad of symptoms:

1. attention deficit,
2. hyperactivity,
3. impulsiveness.

A child with attention deficit very easily distracts under the influence of external stimuli, seems absent, can not absorb complex instructions and commands, loses things needed for work, forgets about everyday matters, commits simple mistakes in tasks and games. Hyperactivity manifested by an inability to sit still in one place and often nervous movements of the limbs. The child is constantly moving, has difficulty engaging in quiet fun, is excessively noisy and running around. Impulsivity manifests, among others, in answering before the question is entirely formulated, interfering with conversation, interrupting others, lack of patience in waiting for your turn, eg in games, games. The condition for the diagnosis of attention deficit hyperactivity is the occurrence of the described symptoms before the seventh year of the child's life and they must significantly impair its functioning in at least two environmental contexts - eg home and school.

There is also an abbreviation ADD in the subject literature. It is used to describe the syndrome in which attention deficit disorders dominate without motor and emotional hyperactivity.

2. Causes of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in children

The reasons for the development of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder are not fully known. These are very complex mechanisms and require knowledge in various fields. It is known for certain that ADHD is a disorder often transmitted from generation to generation, ie genetically determined. In many cases, the environment and education have little to do with the occurrence of symptoms. Recent research has proven that the risk of inheriting ADHD after second-degree relatives is greater after relatives in the male line[5]. Most researchers believe that the cause of

ADHD is the malfunction of connections between nerve cells (neuronal connections), between the brain (especially the frontal lobes) and subcortical nuclei. It also involves improper transmission of information by means of dopamine and norepinephrine (a lowered level of these substances and their derivatives). In children with ADHD, there is also a reduction in the total volume of the brain and cerebellum by about 3-4%. This difference persists throughout life and concerns the cortex of the frontal lobes, subcortical nuclei, cerebellum, as well as the corpus callosum that connects both cerebral hemispheres[6]. During brain function tests, a decrease in blood flow in the frontal lobes and basal ganglia as well as brain glucose was detected in people with ADHD. The cause of the occurrence in children of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder are the CNS, which may be caused by:

1. Factors that damage the nerve cell (nicotine, alcohol, drugs),
2. Diseases during pregnancy (particularly infectious),
3. Poisoning during pregnancy and improper nutrition of the pregnant woman,
4. Mental or hypoxic injuries during delivery,
5. Serious diseases or mechanical injuries of the skull in childhood (eg meningitis, accidents combined with concussion).

Considering the issue of the reasons of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, one can not fail to pay attention to the child's family environment. It is also a fact that in recent times the number of children displaying hyperactivity-related hyperactivity has increased, which according to T. Opolska and E. Potempska, authors of the book entitled "A hyperactive child. Behavior correction program" is a consequence of socio-economic changes, i.e.

1. way of spending free time (television, computer games),
2. pace of life (busy, overworked and exhausted parents),
3. communing with loud and aggressive patterns of interpersonal contacts propagated by the mass media [7].

According to H. Weyhreter, these are effects of:

1. consumer approach to life,
2. growing in the feeling that everything we do must come to us without much effort,
3. decrease in motivation to learn,
4. increased divorce rate,
5. excessive demands made by parents [8].

In the professional literature, it is reported that in the general population of children from 3-8% are children with ADHD. There is also a group of children with so-called the borderline of ADHD, in which the symptoms of hyperactivity are less diverse and intense, and children with symptoms of hyperactive

behaviors, which appeared later, ie after the age of six, and result from social (environmental) sources. Agreeing with modern concepts of ADHD causes, it should not be seen only in the abnormal family environment of the child, but it is also known that a difficult home situation, lack of permanent norms, inconsistency or impulsiveness of the parents themselves may intensify the symptoms of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

3. Characteristics of hyperactive children

The previously quoted DSM-IV and ICD 10 classifications determine attention deficit hyperactivity based on recognized and accepted diagnostic criteria. It is worth noting, however, that there is a difference in the understanding of hyperactivity between the classifications cited. In the WHO definition, the problem of ADHD focuses only on the recognition of hyperactivity, and in it must occur three types of symptoms, ie attention deficit disorder, excessive excitability and impulsiveness. DSM-IV, on the other hand, distinguishes the hyperactivity subtypes that allow to recognize a child with ADHD with the predominance of attention deficit disorders, with the prevalence of motion hyperactivity and excessive impulsivity and a mixed type. Symptoms of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder appear in children before the age of 7.

1. A subtype with the predominance of attention deficit disorders is characterized by the following:

- a child can not focus on what the teacher says, the parent,
- while doing his homework, he is only interested in not working,
- forget what you just talked about,
- do not read the end of, for example, the content of tasks, by which he makes mistakes,
- getting a worse grade at school, because he can not "finish" the task properly,
- gives the impression of "rocking" in the clouds.

Children from this subtype usually do not run aimlessly, as they calmly sit in a bench or at a desk, which is why they do not arouse anxiety parents and teachers. However, they are assessed as less capable and less knowledgeable with science. Distractions of concentration also cause that the child does not use their potential.

2. A subtype with the prevalence of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is characterized by the following symptoms:

- the child is still in motion (eg runs around, jumps on the couch watching TV, walks around the classroom during the lesson),
- enjoys fun, entertainment related to movement, speed,
- gives the impression of being tireless.

Children from this subtype do not usually have difficulty mastering the program material at school, but they get bored quickly and interrupt the teacher's

lesson. In contrast to the previous subtype, these children can focus on what is interesting for them and new, motivated, for example, they can do all the homework from the beginning to the end.

3. Mixed subtype

In both the child has severe symptoms of restlessness, attention deficit disorder and poor impulse control. This type of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is most common.

Studies of psychomotor hyperactive children prove that none of the subtypes is permanent. This means that in a child in subsequent tests, every other or several months can be diagnosed with another ADHD subtype. This is related to the fact that at different ages the child is more intense and different problems are visible. Also, ADHD manifests itself in different ways in each gender. In girls there is a subtype with impaired attention with impulsiveness and subtypes with hyperactivity and mixed preference in boys. The term "attention deficit hyperactivity disorder" is defined as a set of symptoms occurring in one, two or all spheres of child's functioning: motor, cognitive and emotional. The most common type is mixed with symptoms manifesting in two spheres, ie cognitive and motor. Selected mixed types are less common, but in a different combination (cognitive-emotional, emotional-motor). The least frequent are demolitions manifesting in three spheres.

- Symptoms of hyperactivity in the motor sphere are: distinct movement anxiety in terms of large and small motility. Children are not able to stay motionless for even a short period of time, getting up from the place, walking around the classroom, running, waving with their hands, jumping or increased minor limb movements (flapping their legs, moving their fingers, constantly dealing with things that lie within their arms or legs, swaying on a chair, etc.)

- Hyperactivity in the cognitive sphere is primarily expressed by difficulties in focusing attention, an increased sense of orientation and rashness and a quickness of thinking. The child is not able to concentrate longer on the performed activity, the smallest stimulus detaches them from the task. These children shift their attention from object to object, give the impression that they are interested in several things at the same time, which contributes to providing incorrect answers or wrong solutions.

- Hyperactivity in the emotional sphere is expressed in uncontrollable, strong emotional reactions, increased expression of feelings and increased emotional sensitivity to environmental stimuli. The movement and cognitive activity accompanying them often manifests in the chaos of thought [9]

The social sphere is closely connected with the emotional sphere. Here also children with ADHD have problems with proper functioning. Within the social

sphere, these children display: a tendency to dominate and control, a tendency to play the role of a group jester or a "local bully", difficulty in cooperating with peers, difficulty in establishing long-term relationships with peers [10].

4. Educating children with hyperactivity

The functioning of a child with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is determined on the one hand by his or her own abilities and on the other hand constantly shaped by experience gained as a result of interaction with the environment. Children with ADHD behave according to a consistent pattern of behavior. Repeated behavior is repeatedly repeated, which makes it difficult for him to adapt to new situations. In his behavior he constantly notices the dissociation between what the child knows and what he does, ie, for example, he knows that certain behavior will meet them consistently and yet he can not refrain from this behavior. It is connected with the difficulty of inhibiting motor and emotional reactions. Such symptoms are present in varying intensity all the time. The hyperactive child has enormous difficulty in organizing his work and all life activity. Therefore, clear rules should be set for each work they do, at the same time expressing the expectations of the parents or the teacher. "There are five principles that should be instilled in a child who is hyperactive, who is advised to do something that requires calm behavior:

1. Sit at the designated place,
2. Take care of your task and nothing else,
3. Look at the support person at work or on the task being performed,
4. Listen - without interrupting - what is being said to you,
5. Work until the task is completed [11].

Due to the disorder, the hyperactive child in most situations does not meet these requirements, which is why his behavior is assessed negatively. Difficulties in adjusting to the school's requirements may also aggravate the discomfort associated with learning-related hyperactivity. These are most often: memory disorders, language disorders (difficulties in building consistent statements, frequent deviation from the topic, failure to follow the rules of conversation, too fast and too loud speaking, difficulties in using prepositions - on, in, apart, and difficulties with words specifying time sequence - before, after, dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, movement clumsiness. The abovementioned difficulties cause problems with mastery of the program material, which means that the child has less chance of experiencing school success, and in some cases this success is impossible. In addition, accusations of laziness, rebuke for behavior that the child either does not affect completely or its impact is very limited and is not able to change lead to the appearance of low self-esteem, lack of motivation and behavioral disorders. The

hyperactive child has big problems with systematizing knowledge. It is worth to inform them about the content they are currently learning, to match and to connect with their existing ones. For many hyperactive children, especially the elderly, it is beneficial to learn about modern ways of effective learning: using a computer, voice recorder, fast reading. Children with hyperactivity often detach themselves from tasks that just happen and engage in other, more attractive ones for them. So you have to help them in establishing a work plan and marking out the activities they have already done. Sometimes even small changes can have a positive effect on the behavior of a child with ADHD. Therefore, it is worth using various forms of checking the message, knowing that the hyperactive child usually concentrates better during the oral response, while during written work he makes mistakes resulting from inattention: he does not read the end of instructions, he is wrong when rewriting. During written works, it is important to shorten their length, devote more time to their implementation, and constantly remind them about checking "[11]. The teaching of a hyperactive child may be taught by a group of peers. It is a teaching model in which children work in pairs; one of them takes the role of a teacher and instructs a friend. They can be equivalents, as well as those selected from children of equal age. It is very beneficial for a hyperactive child to be paired with a conscientious and diligent colleague. Another method can be learning in a collaborative group, when the whole team is divided into 4-5-person teams. Team members mutually motivate and help each other. Due to the difficulties of adaptation, the inability to cooperate and cooperate in a group is often left out of the way of the class, often ignored or explicitly rejected. Because they are often a source of frustration and nervousness, they can be rejected not only by peers but also by teachers and parents. The result is the feeling of being unwanted, unacceptable. Experiencing frustration caused by the failure to satisfy basic psychological needs, such as the need for acceptance, respect, recognition, self-fulfillment, hyperactive children behave aggressively. They take an attitude of struggle with the environment, which criticizes them all the time, judges negatively for the lack of progress in science despite the often high IQ, compares with other students, suspects bad intentions or irritability. "In the teacher's actions towards this category of children, the teacher's attitude towards the child is extremely important: a favorable atmosphere, empathic attitude understood as the ability to empathize with the situation of another person - the child, offering the whole system of "positive reinforcements", approval of the child's behavior - has a special importance for the situation and well-being of "difficult" students - that is, hyperactive psychomotor, and at the same time allows for

maximum development to the best of their ability "[12]. It's best to start working with the hyperactive child from yourself. You must learn to accept each child with its advantages and disadvantages. Children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder should create a friendly and orderly environment. An important condition for success in working with such a child is to adapt the requirements to a specific child and the cooperation of the teacher, parents and specialists (psychologist, speech therapist, therapist, doctor). Only such cooperation can facilitate the child's normal functioning in the environment [13].

5. Methodology of conducting therapeutic classes

If the hyperactive child, despite the efforts of parents and teachers, does not succumb to the normal way of education and they are not able to help him, then systematic therapy is necessary. Choosing the right therapeutic method for a hyperactive psychomotor child is not easy, because it is necessary to take into account the sphere in which hyperactivity occurs and the depth of its severity. Therapy is selected to the specific needs of the child, his personality, individual situation. "One of the most important things is that helping a child should be multi-directional, which is why it should be given by a team of people." In addition to a psychiatrist, the therapeutic team should include a psychologist and pedagogue. [14]. It is also known that only prevention and early start of therapy significantly increases the chances of changing the child's behavior and may prevent the development of a full picture of behavioral disorders. There are no generally valid guidelines that should be used to treat attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. Each therapy should take into account the individual characteristics of a given child. The most important and most commonly used therapies for hyperactive children are:

1. Therapies that support the development of the child's personality, order his relation to himself and to others, and are directed at the so-called social activity of the child. They include:
 - a therapy called the "holding", which consists of "strong" holding the child. Keeping the child in close physical contact is used to allow the child to express aggression openly,
 - family therapy aimed at improving communication in the family and the system of functioning,
 - behavior therapy. Behavior therapy is based on behavioral psychology and teaches self-control and perseverance,
 - other forms of psychotherapy, e.g. child psychotherapy, psychodrama, etc,
2. The second group is therapies that control the child's motor activity and, as a consequence,

improve his ability to focus and concentrate. We distinguish here:

- sensory integration therapy,
- kinesiology,
- eurhythmics,
- therapeutic horsemanship,
- occupational therapy,
- medical pedagogy,
- play therapy,
- alternating relaxation,
- music therapy.

3. The third group is biochemical treatments. They include diet, pharmacology and homeopathic therapy [15]. In recent years, sociotherapeutic forms of helping children and young people experiencing various types of emotional problems and functional disorders in social contacts are becoming more and more popular. Socioterapy as a method of working in a group assumes the implementation of three basic goals:

- Therapeutic - creating the opportunity to relieve tension and to obtain corrective emotional experiences while participating in classes,
- Educational - gaining knowledge about the problem, how to deal with physical and emotional tension,
- Education and development - gaining social skills during classes such as coping with stress, resolving conflicts, releasing tensions, etc. [16].

When conducting classes with hyperactive children, it is important to remember to follow a few rules. It is important that there are no more than eight children in the group. A smaller number of children will prevent some physical exercises, while a larger number of children may make it difficult to maintain attention in the group and reduce the physical safety of children. It is necessary that the classes are conducted by two adults, where the other person is not only a helper but also a model for children who are not always able to do the exercise themselves. All exercises related to physical activity of children should first be presented by the teachers. Remember about frequent rewarding, mainly in the form of social rewards, i.e. praise, smile, and hug. It is worth having reserve exercises in the reserve, if one of the suggested exercises turned out to be difficult or unattractive for children. After each exercise, especially those that teach something new, it is advisable to discuss them. It should be remembered that you have to be prepared for classes because something that was not planned could always happen. We extend the time of classes gradually.

Summary

In summary, attention should be paid to the fact that attention deficit hyperactivity disorder may be a disorder affecting the future life of the person affected. For this reason, it is necessary early to introduce effective methods of dealing with the symptoms of this disorder, to prevent the development of oppositional defiant or behavioral disorders. Due to the prevalence of this disorder, it is necessary to prepare the child's environment for the possibility of deficits and, if they appear, provide the child with proper care and conditions for optimal development. Each time, the therapy that is planned to be implemented should be individually adapted to the child. This is due to the fact that there are several types of motor hyperactivity disorder, and each of the small patients may react differently to the therapy, even in the case of a similar diagnosis.

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The authors have declared no conflict of interest